

Synthesis of pyrimidin-2-ones and imidazolin-2-ones

Raju Harode^{a*} and T. C. Sharma^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Government Arts & Science College, Ratlam-457 001, India

^bSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, India

Manuscript received 2 April 2001 revised 3 August 2001, accepted 15 February 2002

While reaction of chalcone dibromides (1) with urea in acetic acid is known to give 5-aryl-4- α -bromobenzylimidazolin-2-ones (2), that of 4-methoxychalcone dibromides afforded 4-aryl-5-arylmethineimidazolin-2-ones (4) and 4,6-diaryl-5-bromo-5,6-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones (5).

The reaction of urea with various carbonyl compounds have been studied by earlier workers¹, probably with a view to synthesizing heterocyclic compounds containing -N-C-N- grouping. Dora *et al.*² carried out condensation of chalcone dibromides with urea in acetic acid medium to yield 5-aryl-4- α -bromobenzylimidazolin-2-ones.

In continuation of our work on the reactions of chalcone dibromides³, we now have studied the reaction between chalcone dibromide (1) and urea in acetic acid medium. The products were characterized as 5-aryl-4- α -bromobenzylimidazolin-2-ones (2) as reported earlier². This is attributed to the fact that the formation of urea anion is impossible in acidic medium and thus, the possible attack of urea on the carbon bearing halogen would be different which leads to formation of compounds 2a-c. Interestingly, under identical conditions, when urea was made to react with 4-methoxychalcone dibromides (3), the reaction path altered with isolation of two entirely different compounds, characterized as 4-aryl-5-arylmethineimidazolin-2-ones (4) and 4,6-diaryl-5-bromo-5,6-dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)-ones (5). It is presumed that the possible attack of urea on carbon bearing halogen would be different due to the presence of methoxy group in aryl ring of chalcone dibromide. Reaction of 4'-methoxychalcone dibromide with urea in acetic acid medium, did not afford any product. This is attributed to the fact that due to the presence of 4'-methoxy group, the initial attack at the carbonyl function of chalcone dibromide is precluded.

IR spectra of 4 did not display any peak in carbonyl region, indicating the absence of amide carbonyl group and revealed broad band at 3400 cm⁻¹ (enolic OH), confirming the existence of enolic tautomer. PMR spectra of 4 displayed multiplets at δ 7.5-8.4 due to aromatic protons and sharp peaks at δ 7.0 (=CH-Ar) and 7.2 (OH). IR spectra of 5 exhibited sharp bands at 1730 (C=O) and 3300 cm⁻¹ (NH).

PMR spectra of 5 displayed multiplets at δ 7.5-8.3 due to aromatic and imine protons, a doublet at 7.2 for -CHBr and broad signal at 6.8 instead of doublet due to NH proton.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer.

5-Aryl-4- α -bromobenzylimidazolin-2-ones (2): A mixture of 1,3-diphenyl-2,3-dibromo-1-propanone (1.82 g, 0.005 mol) and urea (0.3 g, 0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting white crystalline solid was washed with pet. ether (b.p.60-80°) and vacuum-dried. TLC showed a single spot: **2a** (61%), m.p. 280° (lit.² 280°), m.m.p. 280°; **b** (50%), 192°; **c** (45%), 273°.

4-Phenyl-5-p-methoxyphenylmethineimidazolin-2-one (4) : A mixture of 4-methoxychalcone dibromide (1.99 g, 0.005 mol) and urea (0.3 g, 0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting white solid was washed with ethanol and crystallized from ethanol to give white crystals : **4a** (30%), m.p. > 260° (Found : C, 73.18; H, 4.97; N, 9.84. C₁₇H₁₄N₂O₂ requires : C, 73.38; H, 5.03; N, 10%), δ (TMS; DMSO-*d*₆) 6.9 (1H, s, CH), 7.0 (1H, s, OH), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.3–8.2 (9H, m, ArH), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3420, 3010, 1600, 1520, 1400, 1350, 1300, 1250, 1050, 840 and 700 cm⁻¹; **b** (32%), > 260°, δ (TMS; DMSO-*d*₆) 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.0 (1H, s, CH), 7.15 (1H, s, OH), 7.5–8.4 (8H, m, ArH), *m/z* M⁺ 312 (77%), 313 (43%), 314 (24%), 297 (8.4%), 298 (3.5%), 268 (7.9%), 269 (3.2%), 270 (5.7%); **c** (28%), > 260°.

4,6-Diaryl-5-bromo-5,6-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (5) : Filtrate of **4a** on concentration yielded yellow solid which was crystallized from ethanol to yield **5a** (28%), m.p. 230° (Found : C, 56.32; H, 3.90; N, 7.25. C₁₇H₁₅BrN₂O₂

requires : C, 56.98; H, 4.18; N, 7.82%), δ (TMS; DMSO-*d*₆ + CHCl₃) 7.2 (1H, d, CHBr), 6.8 (br, CHAr) and 7.5–8.3 (10H, m, ArH and NH), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3320, 2940, 1740, 1600, 1520, 1320, 1260, 1200, 1060, 850 cm⁻¹; **b** (20%), 255°, **c** (22%), 240°.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.H.) is thankful to U.G.C., Regional Office, Bhopal for financial assistance.

References

1. H. K. Mitchell and J. F. Nyc, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 674; B. K. Pattanayak, D. N. Rout and G. N. Mahapatra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, **16**, 1030; F. G. Badder, F. H. Al-Hajjar and N. R. El-Rayyers, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 257.
2. E. K. Dora, B. Dash and C. S. Panda, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1983, **20**, 691.
3. T. C. Sharma and M. M. Bokadia, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, **14**, 66; R. Harode and T. C. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 1144.